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La transformación del papel de la familia en el espacio sociocultural moderno

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Resumen. Se describe la evolución de la percepción de los valores familiares entre la juventud moderna en el espacio sociocultural. Examina cómo las influencias sociales contemporáneas, incluida la educación secular y la cultura consumista, afectan las actitudes hacia la formación de la familia, sus funciones y responsabilidades. Se empleó un método de investigación empírica mediante una encuesta en línea distribuida a 380 estudiantes de la Universidad Politécnica de Moscú. Se estructuró en tres bloques temáticos: (1) comprensión conceptual de la familia y orientaciones de valores, (2) situaciones familiares individuales de los encuestados, y (3) tradiciones familiares y actitudes hacia el divorcio. Los resultados revelan que, a pesar de las tendencias individualistas y consumistas dominantes, el 82,6% de los encuestados sigue considerando la formación de la familia un objetivo vital central. La percepción de la estructura familiar ha cambiado, y sólo el 69,8% afirma la necesidad de un hogar biparental. Un porcentaje notable da prioridad a la carrera profesional y a la realización personal antes que, al matrimonio temprano, y muchos retrasan la formación de una familia hasta una edad más avanzada. El estudio subraya la preocupación por el aumento de las

tasas de divorcio, citando como causas principales la falta de entendimiento mutuo (73,6%) y la infidelidad (11,5%). Los resultados permiten una comprensión amplia de la dinámica familiar y de los retos a los que se enfrenta la cohesión social, aporta ideas relevantes para el trabajo social y los estudios interdisciplinarios sobre la estabilidad familiar y la preservación de los valores.

Palabras clave: transformación familiar, percepción juvenil, valores familiares, espacio sociocultural, autorrealización.

The transformation of family role in the modern socio-cultural space

Abstract. The evolution of the perception of family values among modern youth in the sociocultural space is described. It examines how contemporary social influences, including secular education and consumerist culture, affect attitudes toward family formation, its functions, and responsibilities. An empirical research method was employed through an online survey distributed to 380 students from Moscow Polytechnic University. It was structured into three thematic blocks: (1) conceptual understanding of the family and value orientations, (2) individual family situations of the respondents, and (3) family traditions and attitudes toward divorce. The results reveal that, despite dominant individualistic and consumerist trends, 82.6% of respondents still consider family formation a central life goal. The perception of family structure has changed, and only 69.8% affirm the need for a two-parent household. A notable percentage prioritizes professional careers and personal fulfillment over early marriage, and many delay family formation until a later age. The study highlights concern about rising divorce rates, citing lack of mutual understanding (73.6%) and infidelity (11.5%) as the main causes. The results allow for a broad understanding of family dynamics and the challenges facing social cohesion, providing relevant insights for social work and interdisciplinary studies on family stability and the preservation of values.

Key words: family transformation, youth perception, family values, socio-cultural space, self-realization.

INTRODUCTION

The main issue raised in this paper is the question of how the concept of family remains a traditional value in modern society. The understanding of what family is and what role it plays in a person's life has significantly changed in recent years under the influence of society, culture, and education. It is known that in Christian culture, the family is an important traditional value, as it serves as a foundation not only in the material world but also in the spiritual realm. In this article, the authors analyze how seriously modern youth approach the idea of starting a family, as well as how contemporary society understands the concept of "family."

In the study, the authors relied on works from contemporary scientific literature, as they thoroughly examine the role of Christianity in the upbringing of family values (Kozyrev, 2008; Sushkova, 2013; Zerkina, 2023), the importance of preserving traditions in the family as a factor in raising the next generation (Kulakovskaya-Dyakonova, 2016; Mindibekova, 2016; Gvozd & Semkina, 2021). Many researchers consider the family in the context of spiritual values and traditions (Khasbulatova & Isakieva, 2012; Pashkova, 2017; Abdullaeva & Baytazieva, 2020). There is a large number of studies in the field of ethnography (Afanasyeva, 2005; Krechetova, 2020; Saifutdinova & Syraeva, 2021; Smolyakova, 2021). In modern science, in the fields of pedagogy, psychology, and sociology, there is an increasing number of articles that raise and discuss the issues that contemporary families face. Scholars reflect on how much the institution of family has been deformed in the modern world (Popkova, 2013; Eromasova, 2016; Smolik, 2016; Lyubavina & Belova, 2020; Kabanova, 2024).

The purpose of the article was to identify the problems that are destroying the family, as people in modern society are often unable to find the right solutions when facing them, since traditional views, which were created and cultivated over centuries under the influence of religious culture, have undergone certain transformations. A significant role in this has been played by the decline of morals in the modern consumer society and individualism.

METHODS

The primary research method was an online survey, which involved students from the Moscow Polytechnic University. The study included 380 respondents from the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th years.

The respondents were presented with questions offering multiple-choice answers (both multiple and limited options), as well as open-ended questions. The anonymous questionnaire was conducted remotely using the Google Forms platform, with a standardized questionnaire format. After the survey was posted on Google Forms, students received a link through which each student could complete the survey individually and anonymously. The quantitative data was processed using standard mathematical and statistical analysis methods. The initial data was processed using Microsoft Excel.

The survey consisted of three blocks, all centered around the theme of “family.” The first block contained questions about the concept of family, as well as the value orientations of modern youth. These questions included: What does an ideal family look like? Do you think that a family should be complete? At what age would you like to start a family? How many children should ideally be in a family under current living conditions?

The second block of the survey focused on the individual family situation of the students at the Moscow Polytechnic University. These questions were directly related to each respondent’s specific family situation: In what kind of family did you grow up? What type of family does your family belong to? Would you like to create a family similar to your own?

The third block dealt with leisure time and family activities, family traditions, and issues related to divorce. It raised questions such as: How important is it for you to maintain family ties? How often do you spend time with your family? Are there traditions in your family? What are the reasons for divorces?

Thus, while the first block focuses on the value orientations of modern youth, the second block investigates the factors that shaped these values. The third block aims to uncover the psychological atmosphere in the family where the respondent was raised, which in turn helps to identify the outcomes of modern youth upbringing and the reasons behind the high number of divorces in contemporary society.

RESULTS

Traditional family values are closely tied to religious upbringing. For instance, in Orthodox teaching, family values play a significant role and are deeply rooted in traditional beliefs. The creation of a family plays an important role in shaping a person's spiritual world; it is not an end in itself but a means to achieve well-being and salvation. The family is the environment that shapes a person's inner state.

One of the fundamental values is love and respect within the family. Orthodox Christianity teaches mutual support, compassion, and acceptance of one another within the family circle. There must be a hierarchy within the family for it to be considered complete and harmonious (Lykova et al., 2023).

From the perspective of Orthodoxy, special attention should be paid to the upbringing of children. Parents should serve as role models for their children, raising them in an atmosphere of faith, love, and mutual respect. They must be the first mentors and teachers to their children in understanding Christian and worldly values. The family is the social unit where a new individual's development takes place. The process of socialization, which is so important, begins in the family and largely determines the child's spiritual and mental health.

Furthermore, family traditions such as common gatherings, celebrating Christian holidays together, and participating in church rituals also play an important role in forming a sense of community and strengthening family bonds (Agre et al., 2023).

Thus, family values in Orthodox Christianity represent a comprehensive approach to strengthening family relationships based on love, faith, and respect for loved ones.

This is why we were interested of how does the concept and perception of family has changed in modern society.

The analysis of the survey results from students at Moscow Polytechnic University shows that the students believe the institution of the family is one of the most important traditional values that must be defended and preserved from destruction in the modern world. The majority of respondents consider starting a family to be one of the main goals of their life (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Main goals of life

Even though consumerism is currently the dominant value in modern society, with the principle of individual consumption of material goods increasingly encompassing the rapidly developing trends of the modern world, a significant portion of the youth surveyed still views starting a family as one of the fundamental parts of human life (82.6%). However, career and self-realization are also important to the respondents (74.4%).

Health and a healthy lifestyle rank third in popularity, which is undoubtedly linked to the growing trend of promoting a healthy lifestyle and self-care. For half of the respondents, friends are considered an important aspect of life (46.5%), and for a third, education is crucial (29.1%).

It is noteworthy that religion is ranked fifth, indicating the secular nature of society, which is primarily influenced by atheistic upbringing.

Figure 2. The youth's perception of family

In order to understand what modern youth consider to be most important in family relationships, they were asked what, in their opinion, lies behind the concept of an "ideal family" (Mokhov et al., 2024). According to the survey results, approximately 80% of respondents believe that mutual understanding, respect, love, and care for one another define an ideal family. Nearly half of the res-

pondents think that the loyalty of partners and the health of all family members are crucial to the idea of an ideal family. For 41.9% of respondents, well-being and financial stability are considered key, and only 25.6% believe that having both parents is essential, while 16.3% view legal marriage as important, which suggests that, for them, marriage is merely a formality and not a necessity for creating a family.

Nowadays, almost everyone has encountered the concept of a “single-parent family.” In the modern world, a single-parent family is becoming the norm for the younger generation. However, 69.8% of respondents believe that a family should have two parents.

Figure 3. The importanec of full-fledge family

Do you think the family should be full-fledged?

In the past century, most people used to start their families at an early age (18-23 years), but the situation is somewhat different now. Only 9.3% of young people are ready for early marriage, while 52.3% and 27.9% plan to marry at a more mature age (23-27 years and 28-35 years, respectively). This is likely due to the desire of respondents to first become a complete person, get an education, build a career, and only then think about starting a family (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Age to start a family

At what age would you like to start a family (get married)?

It is also noteworthy that 8.1% of the respondents do not plan to start their own families at all. Regarding children, 9.2% of respondents believe there should be one child in a family, 43.7% believe there should be two, 11.5% think three or four children is ideal, and 18.3% feel that having children is not necessary or that, under current conditions, not having children is the best option. Additionally, 16% of respondents found it difficult to answer and stated that the number of children depends entirely on the family's financial situation.

To understand the reason behind this phenomenon, we asked a slightly different question, creating ideal socio-economic conditions. In this scenario, the number of respondents supporting the idea of having more than three children in a family significantly increased (from 11.5% to 34.4%). This suggests that the respondents would like to have larger families, but due to the current social, political, and economic issues in the country, the younger generation is afraid of difficulties, trials, and does not want to face financial problems. They aspire to a more comfortable life.

The next block of the survey aimed to reveal the individual situations in the families of the respondents. Based on the collected data, the respondents can be divided into three categories: 68.6% grew up in complete families, 24.4% in single-parent families, and 6% experienced both types of families at different times. This situation shows that one-third of the respondents grew up in single-parent or partially complete families. No matter how much parents in incomplete families try to give their children as much love and care as possible, the child will still grow up differently from their peers from complete families. At the level of world perception, they will realize that something is different in their family compared to others, and there are no positive aspects in their family that others consider normal. All of this, directly or indirectly, affects the future and mental health of the child. The child does not learn the norms of behavior for men and women in complete families, does not understand the responsibilities of men and women, and does not have a full understanding of male and female psychology and gender differences. Girls often take on male responsibilities, showing assertiveness and excellent business skills, striving to become the head of the family, while boys become strongly attached to their mothers, who continue to influence their sons even in adulthood, even when they start their own families.

Regarding the type of family: 18.4% belong to traditional families where the husband is the head, 55.2% to egalitarian families (husband and wife are equal), of which half are nuclear families and half are extended families. It is also worth noting that half of the families are small, 28.7% are large families, and the remaining part refrained from answering.

Figure 5. Would you like to have the same family for yourself as the one you grew up in?

This question revealed that 40.2% of respondents would not want to create a family similar to the one they grow up in, while 47.1% would like to have a similar family. 12.6% of respondents were unsure about their answer. These figures suggest that there are still some issues regarding relationships within families. However, despite these concerns, half of the respondents would still like to have families like their own.

The third block of the survey focused on leisure and time spent within families. It should be noted that many students from the Moscow Polytechnic University live in other cities and become quite distant from their families during their studies. However, the students' childhood and adolescence, as well as their formative years, were spent with their families, which undoubtedly influenced the worldview of the respondents.

According to the research, not all respondents consider maintaining family ties an essential part of any family. Among those surveyed, only 67.8% stated that it is important to them. The remaining respondents either disagreed with this view or were uncertain about it. These results confirm the fact that the family dynamics in modern society have changed significantly.

Among those who frequently spend time with their families, 64.3% reported doing so. The remaining 35% prefer to spend time with friends or acquaintances rather than with family. This situation largely defines the individualistic mindset of young people. Family ties are weakening under the influence of modern trends. Categories such as career, success, social connections, and money are becoming more important and valuable than familial bonds and traditions.

Another important aspect is how respondents spend their leisure time with their relatives. According to the survey, the majority are content with simple activities such as spending time together as the family, watching TV, or having conversations (77%), trips to the countryside (34.5%), doing household chores (43.7%), going shopping (43.7%), or meeting with relatives (43.7%). Some attend cultural events together (16.1%), but there are also those who do not spend time together at all (12.6%). In any case, the majority of respondents make an effort to spend time together. It is worth noting that this time spent together mostly revolves around living together and daily household activities, while cultural and religious events represent a small percentage of the total time spent (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Spending time with family

The next block of questions focused on the preservation of the family. Education seems to be an important factor in the strength of family bonds for 51.7% of young people, while it does not play a role for 48.3%. This fact suggests that most respondents believe that having an education for both partners can contribute to the formation of a strong family. This undoubtedly affects the quality of life, income, and financial stability of the family.

Another issue facing modern society is divorce. According to the survey, only one in five respondents has never encountered a case of divorce (Figure 7). The rest, to varying degrees, have witnessed this phenomenon, with 45.9% having experienced it multiple times (Kirillova et al., 2025).

Figure 7. Divorce frequency

Do you have any relatives/friends who are divorced?

Almost all respondents acknowledge that divorce impacts the emotional and psychological state of a child. Only 9.2% hold a different opinion.

The main reason for divorce, according to respondents, is a lack of mutual understanding (73.6%) and infidelity (11.5%). Other reasons mentioned include addiction (4.6%), financial problems (1.1%), and so on.

Thus, it can be concluded that today, issues related to the institution of the family are highly pressing. The problems of demographic decline and divorce have a significant impact on both the social and cultural landscape of individuals and humanity.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the evolving concept of family in modern society, particularly among youth. Despite the growing influence of consumerism and individualism, which emphasize personal achievement and material success, the traditional family unit remains an essential aspiration for a significant portion of young people.

The research also reveals a shift in family formation patterns, with many respondents opting to delay marriage and children in favor of career and self-realization. This reflects broader socio-

economic pressures and the desire to achieve personal stability before starting a family. Furthermore, concerns over divorce are prevalent, with respondents citing mutual understanding and infidelity as key reasons behind family breakdowns.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Abdullaeva, N. A., & Baytazieva, Z. A. (2020). The Role of Traditions in Raising Children in a Modern Family. In: Arsaliev, Sh. M. Kh., Alikhanova, R. A. (Eds.) *Amily of the XXI century: Problems and prospects. Proceedings of the All-Russian scientific and practical conference with international participation dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the Victory in the Great Patriotic War and the 40th anniversary of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "ChSPU"* (pp. 3-7). Grozny: Chechen State Pedagogical University.
- Afanasyeva, A. B. (2005). Child in a peasant and urban family in the aspect of ethnocultural traditions. In: Sultanov, K. V. (Ed.) *Childhood and society: Sociocultural context. Proceedings of the XII International Conference "Child in the modern world. Family and children"* (pp. 207-213). St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg State Polytechnical University.
- Agre, N., Lykova, I., Mayer, A., & Mashkova, D. (2023). "Methods for the study of family upbringing traditions in teaching preschool children". *Nuances: Estudos Sobre Educação*, 34(00), e023009. <https://doi.org/10.32930/nuances.v34i00.10182>
- Eromasova, A. A. (2016). The danger and safety of national spiritual traditions in the family. In: Delova, A. Yu., Borodulin, D. A. (Comp.) *Sakhalin Cyril and Methodius Readings: On the 155th anniversary of the visit of Saint Innocent (Veniaminov) to Sakhalin. Proceedings of the regional scientific and practical conference: Collection of reports* (pp. 26-28). Izhevsk: OOO Print-2.
- Gvoz, S. A., & Semkina, I. A. (2021). The danger and safety of national spiritual traditions in the family. In: *Improving the quality of professional training of specialists in the social and educational spheres. Collection of scientific articles* (pp. 112-116). Vitebsk: Vitebsk State University named after P.M. Masherov.
- Kabanova, K. V. (2024). Family traditions as a socio-cultural practice of counteracting destructive social manipulations in a young family. In: *Young family in the views of modern youth. collection of materials of the All-Russian scientific conference* (pp. 123-128). Ivanovo: Ivanovo State University.
- Khasbulatova, Z.I., & Isakieva, Z. S. (2012). "The Role of the Family in the Process of Spiritual and Moral Education and Transmission of Cultural Traditions to Young People". *History of Science and Technology*, 7, 186-190.
- Kirillova, E., Tkachev, V., Kovaleva, O., Telegin, R., & Timkin, A. (2025). Principles of using mediation platforms based on artificial intelligence in resolving family disputes. *Interacción Y Perspectiva*, 15(1), 67-74. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14031006>
- Kozyrev, F. N. (2008). *Marriage and Family in the Orthodox Tradition*. Moscow: Eksmo.
- Krechetova, G. A. (2020). Ethnocultural traditions as a fundamental element of spiritual and moral education in the family. In: Arsaliev, Sh. M. Kh., Alikhanova, R. A. (Eds.) *Family of the XXI century: Problems and prospects. Proceedings of the All-Russian scientific and practical conference with international participation dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the Victory in the Great Patriotic War and the 40th anniversary of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "ChSPU"* (pp. 215-220). Grozny: Chechen State Pedagogical University.

- Kulakovskaya-Dyakonova, A. Z. (2016). "Ethnopedagogical traditions in increasing the pedagogical potential of the family". *Pedagogical education in Russia*, 1, 179-182.
- Lykova, I., Mayer, A., Shestakova, O., & Voinova, A. (2023). "Developing A Diagnostic Complex for the Study of Family Upbringing Traditions". *Revista on Line de Política E Gestão Educacional*, 27(00), e023068. <https://doi.org/10.22633/rpge.v27i00.18802>
- Lyubavina, N. V., & Belova, Yu. A. (2020). "Family Traditions in the Context of the Transformation of the Family Institution: A Comparative Analysis of the Opinions of the Older and Younger Generations". *Humanitarian Balkan Studies*, 4 (3(9)), 59-63.
- Mindibekova, E. I. (2016). Family in the system of factors ensuring gender socialization of youth: Traditions of the ethnic group and the realities of life. In: Ekeeva, E. V. (Ed.) *Pedagogy of love: Proceedings of the Interregional scientific and practical conference "X Volkov ethnopedagogical readings"* (pp. 42-44). Gorno-Altai: Gorno-Altai State University.
- Mokhov, A., Svirin, Y., Sorokin, V., Artyukhov, E., & Pekshev A. (2024). "Functional approach to understanding the essence of family". *Interacción y Perspectiva*, 14(3), 692-704. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11155223>
- Pashkova, M. I. (2017). Family in the system of factors ensuring gender socialization of youth: Ethnic traditions and realities of life. In: Petrova T.N., Skvortsova, O. V., Nikitin, A. P., Dimitrieva, O. A. (Eds.) *Ethnopedagogy as a factor in preserving Russian identity. Collection of materials from the International scientific and practical conference dedicated to the 90th anniversary of the birth of academician G. N. Volkov* (pp. 454-459). Cheboksary: Chuvash State Pedagogical University named after I.Y. Yakovlev.
- Popkova, A. A. (2013). Transformation of family traditions in Russian families of the XXI century. In: Zamaraeva, Z.P., Grigorieva, M.I. (Eds.) *Social security and protection of family interests in the context of the new social reality. Collection of materials of the V international scientific and practical conference* (pp. 152-156). Perm: Perm State National Research University.
- Saifutdinova, I. R., & Syraeva, A. B. (2021). The Role of the Family in Preserving the Native Language and Folk Traditions. In: Solomenko, L. D., Vodolazko, M. N. (Eds.) *Education of the Younger Generation Based on the Family Traditions of the Writer S. T. Aksakov and the Sociocultural Foundations of the Peoples of Russia (on the 230th Anniversary of the Birth of S. T. Aksakov). Collection of Scientific Articles of the All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference with International Participation* (pp. 160-164). Ulyanovsk: Ulyanovsk State Technical University.
- Smolik, S. V. (2016). Philosophy of the family: Historical tradition and problems of modernity. In: *Social ontology of Russia. Collection of scientific articles on reports of the X All-Russian Kopilov readings* (pp. 173-182). Novosibirsk: Novosibirsk State Technical University.
- Smolyakova, E. A. (2021). Comparative characteristics of fatherhood traditions in Cossack and mountain families. In: Burlyaeva, V. A. (Ed.) *Caucasian dialogue. Proceedings of the XII International scientific and practical conference* (pp. 350-354). Nevinnomyssk: Nevinnomyssk State Humanitarian and Technical Institute.
- Sushkova, Yu. N. (2013). "Legal Traditions of the Doukhobors in the Sphere of Marriage and Family". *Social and Political Sciences*, 1, 31-37.
- Zerkina, N. N. (2023). Preserving Traditions: Family and Education. In: Zambrzhitskaya, E. S., Zosima, E. M. I. V. (Eds.) *Peter the Great Educational Readings. Orthodoxy and National Culture: Losses and Gains of the Past, the Image of the Future. Collection of scientific papers of the XI International Scientific and Practical Conference* (pp.69-72). Magnitogorsk: Nosov Magnitogorsk State Technical University.